

Role of Milan system reporting for categorizing salivary gland lesions in cytopathology

Dr.KrishnaParekh¹, Dr. AswiniShukla², Dr.ToralJivani³, DrParth Patel⁴ Dr.NehaPandya⁵

¹3rd year Resident, Pathology Department SMMIER (Surat Municipal Institute of Medical Education and Research), Opp. Bombay Market, Umarwada, Surat, Gujarat 395010

²Professor, Pathology Department, SMIMER; Surat

³Associate Professor, Pathology Department, SMIMER; Surat

⁴3rd year Resident, Pathology Department, SMIMER; Surat

⁵Tutor, Pathology Department, SMIMER; Surat

OPEN ACCESS

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Krishna Parekh, 3rd year Resident, Pathology Department SMMIER (Surat Municipal Institute of Medical Education and Research), Opp. Bombay Market, Umarwada, Surat, Gujarat 395010

Received: 20-11-2024

Accepted: 25-12-2024

Available online: 31-12-2024

©Copyright: IJMPR Journal

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Salivary glands are exocrine organs responsible for the production and secretion of saliva and consist of the parotid, submandibular, sublingual and minor salivary glands that are numerous and widely distributed throughout the mouth and oropharynx.

Salivary glands neoplasms accounts for less than 3% of all the head and neck tumors. ⁽¹⁾ FNAC is a useful method for evaluating suspicious salivary gland lesions due to its low cost, minimum morbidity, rapid turn around time, high specificity and sensitivity. ⁽²⁾ Among the primary epithelial tumors, 64-80% occurs in the parotid glands, 7-11% occurs in the submandibular, less than 1% occurs in the sublingual and 9-23% occur in the minor salivary glands. ⁽³⁾

Material and Method: The study was conducted on salivary gland lesions over the period of 6 months, with total number of 35 cases in the Department of Pathology.

Results: There is a definite male predominance in lesions of salivary glands.

Parotid is the most common site for occurrence of salivary gland lesions.

Benign neoplasm more common in age group below 50 years and malignancies in above 50 years of age groups.

A total 35 salivary gland lesions were examined and 22 were males and 13 were females. According to MILAN system majority of cases belongs to Neoplasm benign (37%) followed by non neoplastic (28.6%), malignant (25.7%), non diagnostic (5.8%) and Suspicious of malignancy (2.9%).

Conclusion: FNAC has an immense significance as a primary and most effective as well as cost effective screening test in detecting and differentiating salivary glands lesions.

The high sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of cytologic reporting of salivary gland lesions based on Milan nomenclature in our study reflect the positive contribution of the MSRSGC towards accurately categorizing the lesions by which risk of malignancy can be assessed. This helps the clinicians for further management

Keywords: MILAN-Salivary gland, FNAC, Diagnostic accuracy

INTRODUCTION

Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) is a minimally invasive technique. FNAC is a useful method for evaluating suspicious salivary gland lesions due to its low cost, minimum morbidity, rapid turn around time, high specificity and sensitivity. ⁽²⁾

To address the need for a diagnostic framework, the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology was developed in 2015 by an international task force of cytopathologist, surgical pathologist and head and neck surgeons through the American Society of Cytopathology and International Academy of Cytology. ⁽⁴⁾

This comprised of six categories;

1. Non diagnostic (category I)
2. Non- neoplastic (category II)
3. Atypia of undermined significance(category III)
4. Benign neoplasm (category IVa)
5. Salivary gland neoplasm of uncertain malignant potential(SUMP) (category IVb)
Suspicious for malignancy (category V)
6. Malignant (category VI)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During this study 35 patients with salivary glands lesions, of all ages and both gender were included.

Prior informed consent was also taken after explaining the whole procedure. No anesthetic medication was used during the procedure.

FNAC was performed after evaluating detailed clinical history and clinical examination using 22 gauge needle and 10ml plastic syringe with a detachable syringe holder.

All the smears were stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin stain and Giemsa stain and PAP stain.

Site and gender wise distribution of the salivary gland lesions along with the cytomorphological features were charted in the table format.

Further this lesion categorized using Milan system for reporting and compared with other study.

RESULTS

Site wise incidence of salivary swellings

Cytodiagnosis	Parotid gland	Submandibular gland	Total	
	No. of cases	No. of cases	No. of cases	%
Sialadenosis	0	2	2	5.7
Acute sialadenitis	0	1	1	2.85
Chronic Sialadenitis	1	1	2	5.7
Tuberculous Abscess	1	3	4	11.43
Cystic lesion	2	0	2	5.7
Pleomorphic adenoma	9	2	11	31.4
Warthin's tumor	2	0	2	5.7
Granulomatous sialadenitis	0	1	1	2.85
Suspicious malignancy	0	1	1	2.85
Mucoepidermoid Carcinoma (MEC)	1	0	1	2.85
SCC salivary gland	3	4	7	20
Adenoid cystic Carcinoma	0	1	1	2.85
Total	19	16	35	100

Site wise distribution:

Site	No. of cases	%
Parotid	19	54.28
Submandibular	16	45.72

Gender wise distribution:

Sex	No. of cases	%
Male	22	69
Female	13	31

Distribution of all cases according to the MILAN

Category		No. of cases	%
I	Non-Diagnostic	2	5.8
II	Non-neoplastic	10	28.6
III	Atypia of undermined significance	00	00
IVa	Neoplasm Benign	13	37
IVb	SUMP	0	0
V	Suspicious of malignancy	1	2.9
VI	Malignant	9	25.7

Categorizing of FNAC cases according to MILAN System

Milan Category	No. of cases	Primary FNAC diagnosis	No. of cases
I	2	Cystic lesion	2
II(Non neoplastic)	10	Acute Sialadenitis	1
		Chronic Sialadenitis	2
		Tuberculous abscess	4
		Granulomatous Sialadenitis	1
		Sialadenosis	2
III(AUS)	0	Atypia of undermined significance	0
IVa(Benign Neoplasm)	13	Pleomorphic adenoma	11
		Warthin's Tumour	2
V(Suspicious for malignancy)	1	Suspicious looking squamous cells	1
VI(Malignancy)	9	MEC high grade	1
		Salivary duct carcinoma	8

Sialadenosis(cluster of large vacuolated acinar cells (H & E 40x))

Pleomorphic Adenoma(fibrillary matrix with myoepithelial cells) (Giemsa 40x)

Warthin Tumor (oncocytic cells with abundant granular cytoplasm and well defined borders in a background of lymphocytes) (Giemsa 40x)

Adenoid cystic tumor (Basaloid cells surrounding acellular matrix with cribriform pattern (PAP 40x) and mucous cells contain delicate pink mucinous cytoplasm (PAP 40x))

Mucoepidermoid carcinoma (Bland epidermoid cells with moderate amount of dense cytoplasm)

DISCUSSION

- FNAC has been used widely for over five decades in the initial evaluation and triage of patient with salivary gland lesions.
MSRSGC (Milan system for reporting salivary gland carcinoma) is a six tier system for reporting salivary gland lesions according to risk stratification to provide better communication between clinicians and cytopathologists and ultimately improve patient care.
- In our study, 35 salivary gland lesions were studied using Milan system 22 male (69%) and 13 females (31%) identified, with a male to female ratio of 2:1 this is comparable with a few other published literature. Benign neoplasm is highest diagnosed followed by non neoplastic category (II) followed by Malignancy category (VI) which is similar to study done by northeast India as a retrospective study⁽⁶⁾.

CONCLUSION

FNAC has an immense significance as a primary and most effective as well as cost effective screening test in detecting and differentiating salivary glands lesions.

The high sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of cytologic reporting of salivary gland lesions based on Milan nomenclature in our study reflect the positive contribution of the MSRSGC towards accurately categorizing the lesions by which risk of malignancy can be assessed. This helps the clinicians for further management⁽⁷⁾

REFERENCES

Dr. Krishna Parekh, *et al.*, Role of Milan system reporting for categorizing salivary gland lesions in **469** cytopathology. *Int. J Med. Pharm. Res.*, 5(6): 466-470, 2024

1. Anita Omhare, Sanjeev Kumar Singh, Jitendra Singh Nigam and Ankit Sharma. Cytohistopathological Study of Salivary Gland Lesions in Bundelkhand Region, Uttar Pradesh, India. In: Pathology Research International Volume 2014, Article ID 804265.
2. M.A.S. Frable and W.J. Frable. Fine-needle aspiration biopsy of salivary glands. Laryngoscope 1991;101:245-49.
3. Colella G, Cannavale R, Flamminio F, Foschini M. Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology of salivary Gland Lesions: A systematic Review. Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery. 2010;68(9):2146-2153.
4. Rossi, E., Faquin, W., Baloch, Z., Barkan, G., Foschini, M., Pusztaszeri, M., Vielj, P and Kurtycz, D, 2017. The Milan System for reporting salivary gland cytopathology; Analysis and suggestions of initial survey. Cancer Cytopathology, 125(10), pp. 757-766.
5. Qizibassh AH, Sianos J, Young JE, Archibald SD. Fine needle aspiration biopsy cytology of the major salivary glands. Acta Cytol 1985;29:503-12.
6. Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Care, Vol 8, Issue 3, 465-470, Cytological spectrum of salivary gland lesions according to Milan reporting system: A retrospective study.
7. Cajulis R.S, Gokaslan S.T, Yu G.H, and Hidvegi D. Frias. "Fine needle aspiration biopsy of the salivary glands; a five year experience with emphasis on diagnostic pitfalls," Acta Cytologica. 1997;41(5): 1412-1420.